

A Novel Genetic Evolution and Linear Feedback Shift Register Based Pseudo-random Number Generator for Internet of Things

Abstract—Internet of Things (IoT) devices have increased in number and the areas of their application. For instance, IoT is applied in different domains including agriculture (Agri-IoT), smart homes, smart cities, and environmental monitoring, among others. Although these devices are instrumental in facilitating seamless communication and process automation, security issues remain persistent. Securing data for transmission in IoT requires the use of encryption algorithms. However, conventional encryption algorithms are resource-intensive. That is, processes involved in generating the encryption key to the encryption rounds are hardware and software-intensive and unsuitable for IoT devices with limited resources. In this paper, we proposed a hybrid Genetic Evolution - Linear Feedback Shift Register (GE-LFSR)-based Cryptographically Secure Pseudo-random Number Generator (CSPRNG) for generating 256-bit random numbers for data encryption in IoT devices. A sample test result using Raspberry Pi 3B+ showed that the proposed algorithm is resource-efficient and cryptographically-secured by taking an average time of 0.014307112s to evolve an individual and passed all 15 (plus variant) NIST SP800-22 tests.

Index Terms—Cryptography, Genetic Evolution - Linear Feedback Shift Register (GE-LFSR), internet of things, statistical test

I. INTRODUCTION

WITH the growth in technology and the need to incorporate it in various fields such as in homes, industries, and cities to facilitate processing and effective communication, the necessity of microcontrollers has risen [1], [2]. This has given birth to the Internet of Things (IoT).

IoT is the interconnection of smart devices, sensors and actuators to generate data from physical processes. This data can be processed and shared for automation on farms, industries, and homes with little or no human interventions[3].

Crucial to the operation of the IoT setup is the availability of networks that interconnect the smart devices. These networks can operate in two fundamental forms. That is, Local Area Network (LAN) and Wide Area Network (WAN). Both network types can be employed in an IoT setup. However, in IoT, they are implemented in wireless forms because, for most of IoT systems, the nodes on the network can be mobile and are often deployed in remote hostile areas where the cost of cable implementation is expensive [3].

Data shared on IoT networks are sensitive because IoT domains include Smart homes, smart hospitals, smart factories and Smart agriculture (Agri-IoT) [3]. Therefore, transmitted data can be private industrial data, and sensitive health data, among others. Hence, these data need be kept private and secured during transmission. In this regard, encryption systems such as Symmetric (public key) and Asymmetric (private

key) encryptions are usually employed to ensure the privacy and security of data during transmission such as public key and private key encryption [4]. However, IoT devices are resource-constrained and often rely on battery power, have low processing and storage capabilities. [3]. On the other hand, many encryption algorithms involve complex calculations and random number generation processes which require high power, processing and memory resources.

These limitations should not greatly affect the devices' and installed software's performance or security. The quality of an encryption algorithm depends on the key used for encryption. The key is a random sequence used in the encryption process. These random sequences on which the robustness of the security provided by the encryption depends are generated by Random Number Generators (RNGs) as illustrated in Fig 1. Therefore, a novel RNG tailor-made for IoT devices, considering their resource-constraint nature, will prove valuable in reducing encryption time and resources used.

In IoT, RNGs are employed by various applications and system components in their processes for several purposes ranging from basic system operations to ensuring data security. Two types of random sequences that can be used by applications are True Random Number Generators (TRNG) and Pseudorandom Number Generators (PRNG) [5], [6].

The TRNG produces random sequences by processing physical processes that exist in nature that express unpredictable behavior, hence unpredictable patterns. However, capturing the required length of naturally occurring noise for cryptographic purposes can prove difficult and consumes resources that remain scarce in IoT devices [7].

PRNGs on the other hand rely on mathematical algorithms to produce random numbers. It is less complex and requires fewer hardware components. Compared to TRNGs it has higher speed. In this regard, CPRNG is commonly used for producing cryptographic systems. PRNG however requires a random seed to generate random sequences. PRNGs are less vulnerable to attacks by users who have physical access to devices [7]. Characteristics of a good CPRNG include:

- high entropy
- no repetition in generated strings
- should pass statistical test suite such as NIST SP800-22

In this regard, a novel hybrid Genetic Evolution - Linear Feedback Shift Register (GE-LFSR) based CPRNG for generating 256-bit random numbers for data encryption in IoT devices is proposed.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows: Section II gives a review of PRNG, section III summarises the method used to develop the proposed solution, section IV discusses

the proposed solution, Section V the results obtained from experimentation and finally, section VI gives a conclusion from the work and its limitations.

Fig. 1. This is the caption for one fig.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There have been several works done in the research arena on PRNG. Reviewed literature in this paper explores PRNG in IoT.

In [8] sawtooth map (chaotic map) is used as a local map within a lattice-based CML (Coupled Map Lattice). Here the connection ensures that the lattices are connected. The output was a random sequence that passed the NIST 800-90B test suite with a minimum of 0.954 and a maximum of 0.95.

The potential to use grammatical evolution to generate an initial seed for a pseudo-random number generator is investigated in [9]. The generated initial seed obtained an average entropy value of 7.940560934 for 8-bit entropy. Two PRNGs were created; GE-PRNG and GE-CSPRNG to use the initial seed were created, whose outputs passed the NIST 800-22 and Diehard battery of tests.

In [10], chaotic maps are used to generate random numbers. Because chaotic maps show chaotic behaviour under specified parameter ranges its application in CSPRNG is limited. The authors therefore propose a generalized symmetric chaotic map with an added parameter adaptation feature. A lattice-based structure is employed to link all local maps to their neighbouring nodes through a coupling factor to increase the complexity of sequences generated. Results obtained include large key space and a PRNG that generates pseudo-random sequences while maintaining computational efficiency.

A Linear Feedback Shift Register (LFSR) in encrypting data in IoT devices is proposed in [11]. Here the LFSRs used are two prime number bit LFSRs and a comparator that incorporates inequality in the linear recurrence equation in order to increase the complexity. However, there was an average power consumption of 3.446 watts indicating a 6.98% more power consumption than traditional 12-bit LFSR.

A Linear Feedback Shift Register (LFSR) and Linear Congruential Generator (LCG) are used by the authors in [12]. This hybrid method is used to obtain a large key-space group of numbers. By combining the numbers generated from both, a higher level of secrecy is obtained.

Pseudorandom number generators have been proposed by many researchers proposing the use of different methods to obtain random sequences. These proposals can be grouped based on the method used into chaotic maps, linear feedback shift register, and grammatical evolution, among others.

A. Chaotic Maps for PRNG

Several chaotic maps have been used in the design and implementation of PRNG. Chaotic maps have gained popularity in PRNG because of their sensitivity to change in initial conditions. That is, it exhibits chaotic behaviour to a small change in initial conditions. The popular chaotic map technique commonly used in PRNG is the logistic map.

These researchers modify the logistic map to obtain a version that provides their desired output and includes a pseudo-random number sequence generator based on chaotic-tent system [13], hardware pseudo-random number generator using stochastic computing and logistic map [14], pseudorandomly enhanced logistic map [15], hyper-chaotic modified robust logistic map (HC-MRLM) [16], This popularity is owed to its ability to behave chaotically for a range of parameter values between 3.57 and 4. Although the range is small, research works are being done to increase the parameter range [17]. Other works researchers have done in PRNG using chaotic maps include sawtooth map-based PRNG for IoT, coupled map-based enhanced logistic chaotic map [8].

B. LFSR for PRNG

Other works in the research arena focus on using Linear feedback shift registers to generate random sequences [18]. These researchers rely on the transformation offered by LFSR to produce a source of randomness. Other researchers have taken the hybrid approach by merging or combining LFSR with other methods to achieve a higher degree of randomness [18].

These are finite state machines that go through n cycles for an n -input to generate sequences. Usually employed in PRNG cyclic redundancy checks and cryptography. Generally, it is a shift register, however, taps are selected and XORed with an n th flip-flop. After which it is fed to itself. Binary polynomial $P(x)$ and transition matrix (T) are the two main ways LFSR is represented.

C. GE for PRNG

Grammatical evolution is a form of genetic programming based on grammar. It can be used to evolve several things ranging from computer programs, rulesets, to sentences in languages [19]. Grammatical Evolution takes inspiration from biological evolution, employing Neo-Darwinian principles of genetics uncovered through molecular biologists, to generate a protein from an organism's genetic material. The grammar contains the rules for the development of phenotypes. It provides the flexibility needed to represent something in the evolving population. As a result, the application range of GE is wide, finding applications in engineering design, computer games, finance and PRNG [9].

III. LEAN METHODOLOGY

The lean systemic approach is an improvement methodology that focuses on eliminating waste and inefficiency to arrive at a wasteless production process of high effectiveness [20]. This method involves three main steps; build, measure and learn as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Prio to aiming at proposed model an extensive literature synthesis was carried out to learn several models. A hypothesis was arrived at which was designed and built via a series of experimental versions. A baseline model was achieved and performance evaluation metrics were proposed (NIST SP800-22 tests). After series of measurement using the aforementioned metrics, the model was analyzed and iterated over the same cycle.

The first step (Build) is the construction of the artifact based on a preproposed hypothesis. In our experiments, it is hypothesized that a CPRNG GE that incorporates LFSR in its crossover process will generate a Pseudorandom Number of high entropy for IoT applications. After the building process a baseline entropy value of 7.83 was selected for the binary sequence and the baseline time it takes to evolve an individual of 0.02 was selected. Metrics such as computational time and entropy of binary output are taken, cross-checked with the baseline and analysis is performed to learn from the process. After this, a new hypothesis is proposed to reduce waste and increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the algorithm based on the output. Another hypothesis is formulated until the algorithm is as effective and efficient with little to no waste while meeting baseline requirements.

Fig. 2. Illustration of Lean Methodology Used

IV. PROPOSED MODEL

In this paper, a novel GE-based LFSR is proposed, which generates a random binary sequence using a hybrid GE and LFSR. The concept of using GE for producing random numbers where the evolution uses LFSR. The GE uses GA that searches the space of the syntactically legal structure. The genomes are strings of variable lengths. These are mapped to a phenotype. The grammar is used to guide the mapping process, represented in Backus–Naur Form (BNF) as $\{S, N, T, P\}$, where,
 S = start symbol,
 N = set of non-terminals,
 T = set of terminals,
 P = set of production rules

The production rules are made up entirely of non-terminals that map the start symbol a seed $\langle expr \rangle$. In its operation, the GE evolves populations of the genomes. A fitness test is then performed using the Shannon’s entropy test.

Afterward, they are selected through fitness-based probability for generation of the next generation as illustrated in the block diagram in Fig. 3 and the flowchart given in Fig. 4a. In generating the next generation crossover and mutation to be performed and create a new population as illustrated in Fig. 4b. During crossover, the parents undergo a single-point crossover where a single point in both parents is chosen for division. The two sections of the parent1 are passed through the LFSRs for transformation as can be seen in Fig 4c. There are two different LFSRs ($LFSR_a$ and $LFSR_b$). The first part of parent one is passed through the $LFSR_a$ and the second part is passed through $LFSR_b$. The algorithms for $LFSR_a$ and $LFSR_b$ are given in Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2 respectively.

Fig. 3. Block Diagram for the Proposed Solution

A. Shannon’s Entropy

The function for determining entropy is the Shannon’s entropy function. By determining the entropy for every output we can determine which outputs have high entropy levels. These outputs would then be stored for reseeding the PRNG after a defined period. This period is equal to the number of times a random sequence can be generated before the CPRNG starts repeating random numbers, after which it can be said randomness is not maintained.

Shannon’s entropy function is given in Equation 1. The final entropy function for calculating the normalized entropy of the binary sequence based on Shannon’s entropy function is given in Equation 2.

$$H(x) = - \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \log_2 p_i \quad (1)$$

Fig. 4. Flowchart for the Proposed Solution

Algorithm 1 Algorithm for LFSR_a

Require: input

Ensure: output

- 1: Input: seed, polynomial, length
- 2: $seed_int \leftarrow int(seed)$
- 3: $polynomial_int \leftarrow int(polynomial)$
- 4: Initialize register with $seed_int$
- 5: Initialize result as an empty list
- 6: **for** $i = 1$ to $len(state_len)$ **do**
- 7: $output_bit = register \& 1$
- 8: $result.append(output_bit)$
- 9: $register = register \gg 1$
- 10: $feedback_bit = 0$
- 11: **if** $register \& 1 \neq 0$ **then**
- 12: $feedback_bit = 1$
- 13: **end if**
- 14: **if** $output_bit = 1$ **then**
- 15: $register = register \oplus polynomial_int$
- 16: **end if**
- 17: $register = register | feedback_bit \ll (len(seed) - 1)$
- 18: $binary_sequence = string(result)$
- 19: **end for**
- 20: **return** $binary_sequence$

$$H(x) = - \sum_{i=1}^8 \left(\frac{- \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \log_2 p_i}{n} \right) \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of possible binary permutations in the initial seed. Given a 1 bit, the value of N is 2 since the permutations are $\{0, 1\}$ however for a 2 bit the value of N is given as 4 since the number of binary permutations is

Algorithm 2 Algorithm for LFSR_b

Require: input

Ensure: output

- 1: Input: $binaryString$
- 2: $state \leftarrow int(binaryString)$
- 3: **for** $i = 1$ to $len(state_len)$ **do**
- 4: $binary_sequence = binary_sequence + (state \& 1)$
- 5: $newbit = (state \oplus (state \ll 1)) \oplus (state \gg 3) \oplus (state \gg 7) \oplus (state \gg 5)$
- 6: $newbit = newbit \oplus (state \oplus state \ll 13)$
- 7: $newbit = newbit \oplus (newbit \ll 5)$
- 8: $state = (state \gg 1) | (newbit \ll state_len)$
- 9: $binary_sequence = string(binary_sequence)$
- 10: **end for**
- 11: **return** $binary_sequence$

$\{00, 01, 10, 11\}$. The frequency of 0s and 1s patterns in the binary sequence is given as p_i . The range of bits from 1 to 8 is given as n . Hence the entropy function is the summation for all values of n , H_1 to H_8 divided by n .

Blake is an algorithm that adapts the ChaCha stream, a stream cipher that works by converting 4 words, including XOR and fast implementation of bit rotation [21]. Taking into consideration simplicity and usability while employing the efficiency and security of Blake, blake2 was developed. For 64-bit architectures and smaller architectures blake2b and blake2s were made respectively. In January 2020, the blake3 was announced after having made improvements to blake2 to make it faster. In terms of speed blake3 outperforms blake2 MD5, SHA-1, SHA-2, and SHA-3. It can better secure data than MD5 and SHA-1. In improving the blake2 to obtain blake3 the 10 rounds were reduced to 7 and the input block was divided and hashing them separately into continuous 1KB continuous chunks. In this regard, blake3 is smaller faster and suitable for verification and security, especially in IoT devices [21]. On a Raspberry Pi Zero with a 32-bit ARM1176 processor, Blake3 performed faster than other hash functions as illustrated in Fig 5. Measurement was done in cycles per byte.

V. RESULTS

Using the lean method 5 different versions of the program were made. All 5 versions were made with V1 using SHA-256 to secure the data, the grammar rules in versions 2 and 3 were varied with no LFSR, version 4 had a single LFSR function and secured with Spongent hash and finally V5 which includes LFSR in the crossover to increase the entropy giving a high entropy of up to 7.89 for 20 generations and population size of 16 being secured with Blake3-256 as illustrated in Figure 6.

A sample initial seed generated by the program is given below:

```
011010010101011000001001010100000101111010011101
1001010001100101001110010111101110100000011011100
01101011010101011010001111000000100011100001110101
```


Fig. 5. Comparing throughput of a single-threaded Blake3 with other Hash Functions on AWS c5.metal Instance

Fig. 6. A Graph Illustrating the Average Entropy for 20 Generation Run of the Different Versions

11111010001000011100111100001100111100000001111000
11111100100100110110001010100001101011101101100110
11111101, Fitness: 7.876381235419011

To find the normalized entropy of the sample binary sequence, Equation 2 for finding normalized entropy is applied. Applying Shannon’s entropy we find that for one bit, the number of occurrences of {0, 1} is 129 and 129 respectively giving a frequency of 0.496 and 0.503 respectively hence a value of 1.0 for H_1 . For H_2 the permutations give us {00, 01, 10, 11} with frequencies {63, 64, 63, 65} respectively and a frequency of 0.2478, 0.2509, 0.2475 and 0.2549 resulting in an H_2 value of 0.9999. Following the same procedure, the H value was found for H_3 to H_8 as well. For values from H_1 to H_8 , the corresponding n values were used for division and then summed to obtain a final entropy of 7.8763. Table I illustrates

the calculation for the entropy of the sample generated initial seed.

TABLE I
ENTROPY CALCULATION FOR THE SAMPLE.

No. of bits (n)	H-value	Entropy (H-value/n)	\sum Entropy
1	$H_1 = 1.0$	1.0	1.0
2	$H_2 = 1.9999$	0.9999	1.9999
3	$H_3 = 2.9975$	0.9992	2.9991
4	$H_4 = 3.9903$	0.9976	3.9967
5	$H_5 = 4.9743$	0.9949	4.9915
6	$H_6 = 5.9372$	0.9895	5.9811
7	$H_7 = 6.7952$	0.9707	6.9518
8	$H_8 = 7.3967$	0.9246	7.8764
Final Entropy			7.8763

To find the crossover and mutation rates that give optimum performance, the values were varied. Firstly, the mutation rate was maintained at 0.01 while the crossover rates varied from 0.1 to 1.0. Secondly, the values for crossover were maintained at 0.9 while the mutation rate varied from 0.01 to 0.5.

While experimenting with the crossover and mutation rates, a crossover rate of 0.9 and a mutation rate of 0.01 produced the highest entropy with the optimum evolution time it takes to evolve an individual of 0.014307112s.

The statistical National Institute of Standards and Technology SP800-22 (NIST SP800-22) test suite was used to validate the binary sequence generated using the program. There are 15 main tests in this test suite. The binary sequence produced by the PRNG passed all 15 tests as illustrated in Table II. A comparison of the NIST test result obtained from GE-LFSR PRNG and some existing methods is also given in Table III.

TABLE II
A SIMPLE TABLE EXAMPLE.

No.	Test Items	P-Value	Results
1	Frequency	0.911413	Passed
2	Block frequency	0.534146	Passed
3	Runs	0.911413	Passed
4	Longest run	0.213309	Passed
5	Rank	0.350485	Passed
6	Discrete Fourier transform	0.911413	Passed
7	Non-overlapping template	0.739918	Passed
8	Overlapping template	0.534146	Passed
9	Universal	0.350485	Passed
10	Linear complexity	0.213309	Passed
11	Serial	0.739918	Passed
12	Approximate entropy	0.534146	Passed
13	Cumulative sums	0.350485	Passed
14	random excursions	0.858951	Passed
15	Random excursions variant	0.889129	Passed

Fig7 shows the graph for the average entropy generated by the program using Raspberry pi 3B+. An average entropy of 7.861967643 was achieved using a production size of 7 for 10 generations.

Experiments were performed using raspberry Pi OS, python version 3.10.8. The Raspberry Pi 3B+ and Raspberry Pi 4B were also used with specifications; Broadcom BCM2837B0, Cortex-A53 (ARMv8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.4GHz 1GB LPDDR2

TABLE III
COMPARING GE-LFSR PRNG WITH EXISTING PRNG METHODS

No.	Test Items	GE-LFSR PRNG	[22]	[23]	[24]	[25]	[26]
1	Frequency	0.911413	0.122325	0.9512	0.739918	0.213309	0.000000
2	Block frequency	0.534146	0.534146	0.7645	0.739918	0.534146	0.350485
3	Runs	0.911413	0.407091	0.2429	0.350485	0.008879	0.000000
4	Longest run	0.213309	0.739918	0.0.689	0.534146	0.911413	0.350485
5	Rank	0.350485	0.911413	0.1969	0.350485	0.534146	0.004301
6	Discrete Fourier transform	0.911413	0.299251	0.3306	0.213309	0.350485	0.004301
7	Non-overlapping template	0.739918	0.420549	0.1372	0.350485	0.739918	0.350485
8	Overlapping template	0.534146	0.468595	0.7498	0.350485	0.213309	0.534146
9	Universal	0.350485	0.178278	0.0308	0.534146	0.350485	0.350485
10	Linear complexity	0.213309	0.468595	0.7349	0.739918	0.213309	0.911413
11	Serial	0.739918	0.703397	0.1473	0.350485	0.534146	0.534146
12	Approximate entropy	0.534146	0.671779	0.6111	0.739918	0.035174	0.017912
13	Cumulative sums	0.350485	0.139393	0.4895	0.579749	0.73998	0.000000
14	random excursions	0.858951	0.191373	0.1394	0.583628	—	—
15	Random excursions variant	0.889129	0.195760	0.3431	0.522431	—	—

SDRAM and Broadcom BCM2711, Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.8GHz, 8GB LPDDR4-3200 SDRAM respectively. Table IV shows the average time it takes to produce PRNG for Raspberry Pi 3B+ and Raspberry Pi 4.

TABLE IV
AVERAGE TIME IT TAKES FOR THE PROGRAM TO EXECUTE ON RASPBERRY PI 3B+ AND RASPBERRY PI 4

Device	Run No.	Population	Generation	Avg. Time
Raspberry pi 3B+	20	3	5	0.388202882
		7	10	1.443690479
		16	20	5.642449367
Raspberry pi 4B	20	3	5	0.117854667
		7	10	0.452335441
		16	20	1.641240203

Fig. 7. Graph for Entropy Obtained for 100 runs for a Population Size of 7 for 10 Generations

VI. CONCLUSION

The world is becoming smarter in many domains such as agriculture (Agri-IoT), industries, and smart homes, among others. However, conventional encryption methods are not resource-efficient for low-powered IoT devices. In this regard, a hybrid CPRNG based on GE and LFSR (GE-LFSR) suitable for generating random numbers for cryptography purposes in IoT devices is proposed in this study. The CPRNG has been tested on IoT devices where it takes an average of 0.014307112s to evolve an individual (computationally efficient) and has passed all 15 NIST SP800-22 tests.

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